

Combining recurrent and convolutional neural networks for muscle surrogate modeling

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Abstract— The muscle model developed by Huxley is applicable to the modeling of non-uniform contractions. This model's primary shortcoming is that it requires a significant amount of processing power, particularly when applied to multi-scale finite element simulations. To resolve this, we created surrogate models of Huxley's muscle model, which imitate it but use less computational time and memory. Our

surrogate models are constructed using recurrent and convolutional neural networks. A time series consisting of muscle activation, stretch, stress, and instantaneous stiffness in previous time steps was used as an input to our neural networks. Once the network is successfully trained, it predicts stress and instantaneous stiffness for the current time step, of finite element analysis, based on the input time series. Based on achieved similarities between original and surrogate model, along with achieved speed-up, it can be concluded that our model can be used as a replacement of Huxley's muscle model. To demonstrate the potential of our surrogate models we simulated cardiac cycle of echocardiography-based left ventricle model.

Clinical Relevance— Since, multi-scale simulations are quite computationally intensive, their acceleration via surrogate modeling enables efficient usage in clinical practice. Clinicians can use muscle simulations to examine realistic and hypothetical scenarios regarding cardiac muscle contraction, which can help them make more informed decisions in cardiac disease treatment.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Stojanovic et al. [1,2] presented a multiscale finite element simulation with the Huxley muscle model at the microscopic level. Using muscle activation, stretch, and other material parameters and properties, they utilized Huxley's model to calculate stress and instantaneous stiffness during transient finite element simulation [1]. These simulations with finite elements can be computationally intensive. Calculations at the microscale are the most time-consuming aspect of these simulations. Simulations with hundreds of finite elements and a single time step can take up to several thousand seconds to complete. In our work, to reduce the computational requirements of such simulations, we substituted the actual Huxley muscle model with a surrogate model that is more computationally efficient.

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